

On the Crypto-Automorphism of the Buchsteiner Loops

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Abstract: In this study, New identities of Buchsteiner loops were obtained via the principal isotopes. It was also shown that the middle inner mapping T_v^{-1} is a crypto-automorphism with companions v and v^λ . Our results which are new in a way, complement and extend existing results in literatures.

Key Words: Buchsteiner loop, WWIP-inverse loop, automorphism group, crypto-automorphism.

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§1. Introduction

A binary system (Q, \cdot) is called a loop if $a \cdot 1 = a = 1 \cdot a, \forall a \in Q$, and if the equations $ax = b$ and $ya = b$ have respectively unique solutions $x = a \setminus b$ and $y = b / a, \forall a, b \in Q$. The mappings R_x and L_x for each $x \in Q$, called respectively the right and left translation mappings, are defined as $yx = yR_x$ and $xy = yL_x, \forall y \in Q$, they are one-to-one mapping of Q onto Q . It is important to know that the group generated by all these mappings are called multiplication group $MlpQ$, readers should please see [1,10].

Therefore, a loop (Q, \cdot) is called Buchsteiner loop, if $\forall x, y, z \in Q$, the identity

$$x \setminus (xy \cdot z) = (y \cdot zx) / x \quad (1.1)$$

is obeyed. This loop was first noticed by Buchsteiner [3] in 1976. Thereafter much is not heard of it until 2004, when Piroska Csögo, et al came up with a comprehensive study on this loop structure [5,6]. In fact, they presented for the first time, an example of Buchsteiner loop which is conjugacy closed.

A Buchsteiner loop is isomorphic to all its loops isotopes, hence it is a G -loop. It is not an inverse property loop, however it satisfies a kind of inverse known as *doubly weak inverse property*(WWIP) [5].

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A loop (Q, \cdot) is called *doubly weak inverse property* (WWIP) if the identity

$$(x \cdot y)J_\rho \cdot xJ_\rho^2 = yJ_\rho \quad (1.2)$$

holds $\forall x, y \in Q$. Buchsteiner loop is a class of G -loop which is defined concisely by an equation. This makes the study of Buchsteiner loop interesting since G -loop is not known to be described by a first order sentence [5].

These facts, provided the background to obtain some new identities for Buchsteiner loops. These identities, were in turn used to show that T_v^{-1} is a crypto-automorphism with companion v and v^λ .

Definition 1.1 (1) An isotopism of loops (Q, \circ) and (Q, \cdot) with same underlying set, is a triple (α, β, γ) of permutation of Q satisfying

$$x\alpha \cdot y\beta = (x \circ y)\gamma, \forall x, y \in Q. \quad (1.3)$$

In this case (Q, \circ) and (Q, \cdot) are said to be isotopic.

(2) An isotopism (α, β, γ) is called *principal* if $\gamma = Id_Q$. In such a case $1 \in Q$ is identity of (Q, \circ) , and if we set $1\alpha = u$ and $1\beta = v$, then (1.3) becomes $x \circ y = x/v \cdot u \backslash y = xR_v^{-1} \cdot yL_u^{-1}$, $\forall x, y \in Q$. Here \backslash and $/$ are left and right division operation in (Q, \cdot) . Then the loop (Q, \circ) is called *principal isotope* of (Q, \cdot) .

(3) An isotopism (α, β, γ) of a loop (Q, \cdot) onto itself is called *autotopism*. The set $Atp(Q)$ of all autotopisms of a loop Q is a group.

(4) A permutation α of Q is an *automorphism* if $\alpha \in Aut(Q)$ or if and only if $(\alpha, \alpha, \alpha) \in Atp(Q)$.

Definition 1.2([4]) Let (Q, \cdot) be any loop. A permutation C on symmetric group of Q is called *crypto-automorphism* of Q if there exist m, t in Q , such that for every x, y in Q , we have

$$(x \cdot m)C \cdot (t \cdot y)C = (x \cdot y)C. \quad (1.4)$$

§2. Preliminaries

Lemma 2.1([5]) A loop Q satisfy the identity (1.1) if and only if

$$(L_x^{-1}, R_x, L_x^{-1}R_x) \quad (2.1)$$

is an autotopism $\forall x \in Q$.

Lemma 2.2([5]) A loop (Q, \cdot) satisfies the Buchsteiner identity $x \backslash (xy \cdot z) = (y \cdot zx)/x$, if and only if $(L_x^{-1}, R_x, L_x^{-1}R_x) \in Atp(Q)$, $\forall x, y, z \in Q$.

Theorem 2.1([5]) Let Q be a Buchsteiner loop. Then $\forall x, y \in Q$, $R_{(x,y)} = [L_x, R_y] = L_{(y,x)}^{-1}$.

Note also that, the commutator $[L_x, R_y]$, is defined as $L_xR_y = R_yL_x[L_x, R_y] \Rightarrow L_x^{-1}R_y^{-1}L_xR_y = [L_x, R_y] \Rightarrow L_x^{-1}L_y^{-1}L_{yx} = [L_x, R_y]$, since from Lemma 2.2, $R_y^{-1}L_xR_y = L_y^{-1}L_{yx}$.

Theorem 2.2([2]) *Let $(Q, \cdot, \backslash, /)$ be a quasigroup. If $Q(a, b, \circ) \cong^{\theta} Q(c, d, *)$, then $Q(f, g, \Delta) \cong^{\theta} Q((f \cdot b)\theta/d, c \backslash (a \cdot g)\theta, \square)$. If (Q, \cdot) is a loop, then $(f \cdot b)\theta/d = [f \cdot (a \backslash c\theta^{-1})]\theta$ and $c \backslash (a \cdot g)\theta = [(d\theta^{-1}/b) \cdot g]\theta$, where $a, b, c, d, f, g \in Q$.*

§3. Main Results

Our first main result reads:

Theorem 3.1 *A loop $(Q, \cdot, \backslash, /)$ is a Buchsteiner loop if and only if the identity*

$$u\{x \backslash [(xy)/v \cdot z]\} = \{[(uy)/v \cdot u \backslash \{(uz)/v \cdot u \backslash (xv)\}]/(u \backslash (xv))\}v \quad (3.1)$$

holds $\forall u, v, x, y, z \in Q$.

Proof Suppose $(Q, \cdot, \backslash, /)$ is a Buchsteiner loop with any arbitrary principal isotope (Q, \circ) such that $x \circ y = xR_v^{-1} \cdot yL_u^{-1} = x/v \cdot u \backslash y, \forall u, v \in Q$. Buchsteiner loops are G-loops [5]. Now choose $u, v \in Q$ such that (Q, \circ) is loop isotope of (Q, \cdot) . Therefore, we have $x \backslash [(x \circ y) \circ z] = [y \circ (z \circ x)]/x \Rightarrow x \backslash [(xR_v^{-1} \cdot yL_u^{-1})R_v^{-1} \cdot zL_u^{-1}] = [yR_v^{-1} \cdot (zR_v^{-1} \cdot xL_u^{-1})L_u^{-1}]/x$. Now choose p such that $x \backslash [(xR_v^{-1} \cdot yL_u^{-1})R_v^{-1} \cdot zL_u^{-1}] = p = [yR_v^{-1} \cdot (zR_v^{-1} \cdot xL_u^{-1})L_u^{-1}]/x$, then $[(xR_v^{-1} \cdot yL_u^{-1})R_v^{-1} \cdot zL_u^{-1}] = x \circ p \Leftrightarrow [yR_v^{-1} \cdot (zR_v^{-1} \cdot xL_u^{-1})L_u^{-1}] = p \circ x$. Solving these two separately and equating the answers give

$$u[(x/v) \backslash \{[(x/v) \cdot (u \backslash y)]/v \cdot (u \backslash z)\}] = [\{(y/v) \cdot (u \backslash [(z/v) \cdot (u \backslash x)])\}]/(u \backslash x)v$$

Setting $x' = x/v \Rightarrow x'v = x, y' = u \backslash y \Rightarrow uy' = y$ and $z' = u \backslash z \Rightarrow uz' = z$ in the last expression gives

$$u\{x' \backslash [(x'y')/v \cdot z']\} = \{[(uy')/v \cdot u \backslash \{(uz')/v \cdot u \backslash (x'v)\}]/(u \backslash (x'v))\}v$$

which is the required identity if x', y' and z' are respectively replaced by x, y and z

Conversely, let (Q, \cdot) be a loop which obeys equation (3.1), working upward the process of the proof of necessary condition, we obtain the Buchsteiner identity relation for any arbitrary u, v -principal isotope (Q, \circ) of (Q, \cdot) . \square

Lemma 3.1 *Let (Q, \cdot) be a loop. Then*

(1) *Q is a Buchsteiner loop if and only if, $\forall x, u, v \in Q$, the triple*

$$(R_v L_x^{-1} L_u R_v^{-1}, L_u R_v^{-1} R_{\{u \backslash (xv)\}} L_u^{-1}, L_x^{-1} L_u R_v^{-1} R_{\{u \backslash (xv)\}}) \in Atp(Q). \quad (3.2)$$

(2) *In particular, Q is a Buchsteiner loop if $\forall u, v \in Q$, the triple*

$$(R_v L_u R_v^{-1}, L_u R_v^{-1} R_{(u \backslash v)} L_u^{-1}, L_u R_v^{-1} R_{(u \backslash v)}) \in Atp(Q). \quad (3.3)$$

Proof (1) Suppose the Q is a Buchsteiner loop, then equation (3.1) of Theorem 3.1 holds in (Q, \cdot) . Expressing the equation in term of autotopism gives (3.2). Conversely, suppose the

autotopism (3.2) holds in Q , $\forall u, v \in Q$, taking any $y, z \in Q$ it implies that, $yR_vL_x^{-1}L_uR_v^{-1} \cdot zL_uR_v^{-1}R_{\{u \setminus (xv)\}}L_u^{-1} = (yz)L_x^{-1}L_uR_v^{-1}R_{\{u \setminus (xv)\}}$, the rest is simple.

(2) Suppose the Q is a Buchsteiner loop, then equation (3.1) of Theorem 3.1 holds in (Q, \cdot) , hence the autotopism (3.2) holds in Q . The required result is obtained if we set $x = 1$ in this autotopism. \square

Theorem 3.2 *Let (Q, \cdot) be a loop, (Q, \circ) an arbitrary principal isotope of (Q, \cdot) and $(Q, *)$ some isotopes of (Q, \cdot) . Then (Q, \cdot) is a Buchsteiner loop if and only if the commutative diagram*

$$(Q, \cdot) \xrightarrow[\text{left principal isotopism}]{(R_v, I, I)} (Q, *) \xrightarrow[\text{isomorphism}]{(\eta, \eta, \eta)} (Q, \circ) \xrightarrow[\text{principal isotopism}]{(R_{(u \setminus v)}^{-1}, L_u^{-1}, I)} (Q, \cdot)$$

holds, where $\eta = L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}$, $\forall u, v \in Q$.

Proof Suppose (Q, \cdot) is a Buchsteiner loop, by Lemma 3.1(2) the autotopism (3.3) holds in (Q, \cdot) . Thus, $(R_vL_uR_v^{-1}, L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}L_u^{-1}, L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}) = (R_v, I, I)(\eta, \eta, \eta)(R_{(u \setminus v)}^{-1}, L_u^{-1}, I)$, where $\eta = L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}$. Expressing this in terms of composition supplies the prove of the necessity. Conversely, suppose the commutative diagram holds in Q , we only need to show that the autotopism (3.3) holds in (Q, \cdot) . This is obtained by component multiplication of the compositions of the commutative diagram. \square

Theorem 3.3 *A Buchsteiner loop $(Q, \cdot, \setminus, /)$ obeys the identities: $((uz)/v) \cdot (u \setminus v) = u\{(u[(u \setminus v)/v \cdot z])/v \cdot (u \setminus v)\}$ and $u\{(u \setminus (yv))/v\} = \{(y \cdot u \setminus [(u/v) \cdot (u \setminus v)])/(u \setminus v)\}v$.*

Proof From Theorem 3.2, observed that (Q, \circ) and $(Q, *)$ are principal and left principal isotopes of (Q, \cdot) respectively and $\eta = L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}$ is an isomorphism. Therefore $(Q, 1, v, \circ) \stackrel{\eta}{\cong} (Q, u, u \setminus v, *)$. Let (Q, y, z, Δ) be an arbitrary principal isotope of (Q, \cdot) , comparing these with the statement of Theorem 2.2, we have $a = 1, b = v, c = u, d = u \setminus v, f = y, g = z$ and $\theta = \eta = L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)}$. Using these we can compute: $c \setminus (a \cdot g)\theta = u \setminus (1 \cdot z)L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)} = u \setminus \{(uz)/v \cdot (u \setminus v)\}$ and $[(d\theta^{-1}/b) \cdot g]\theta = \{[(u \setminus v)(L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)})^{-1}]/v \cdot z\}L_uR_v^{-1}R_{(u \setminus v)} = \{u[(u \setminus v)/v \cdot z]/v\}(u \setminus v)$. Hence $c \setminus (a \cdot g)\theta = [(d\theta^{-1}/b) \cdot g]\theta \Leftrightarrow u \setminus \{(uz)/v \cdot (u \setminus v)\} = \{u[(u \setminus v)/v \cdot z]/v\}(u \setminus v) \Leftrightarrow ((uz)/v) \cdot (u \setminus v) = u\{(u[(u \setminus v)/v \cdot z])/v \cdot (u \setminus v)\}$, which proved the first identity. The second is similarly obtained, using appropriate arrangement. \square

Corollary 3.1 *Let (Q, \cdot) be a Buchsteiner loop. Then the identities $(vz)/v = v[(v \cdot v^\lambda z)/v]$ and $v\{(v \setminus (yv))/v\} = yv^\rho \cdot v$ hold $\forall v, y, z \in Q$.*

Proof All of these identities are obtained respectively by identities of Theorem 3.3 by setting $u = v$. \square

Corollary 3.2 *If (Q, \cdot) is a Buchsteiner loop, then*

- (1) $(vz)/v = v[(v \cdot v^\lambda z)/v]$ if and only if $L_v^{-1} = T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}$, $\forall v, z \in Q$;
- (2) $v\{(v \setminus (yv))/v\} = yv^\rho \cdot v$ if and only if $R_v = T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}T_v$, $\forall v, y \in Q$.

Proof Setting $u = v$ in the identities of Theorem 3.3, we obtained $(vz)/v = v[(v \cdot v^\lambda z)/v] \Rightarrow L_v^{-1} = T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}$ from the first one. Conversely, suppose $L_v^{-1} = T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}$

holds in Q , now for any $z \in Q$ $zL_v^{-1} = zT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1} \Leftrightarrow v \setminus z = \{v[v^\lambda(v \setminus (zv))]\}/v$, now set $z = v \setminus (zv)$ and the first identity is obtained. The second assertion is similarly obtained. \square

Corollary 3.3 *Let Q be a Buchsteiner loop, then $(T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}, T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v, T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v) \in \text{Atp}(Q), \forall v \in Q$.*

Proof This is obtained by substituting the assertion of Corollary 3.2 into the autotopism (2.1). \square

Lemma 3.2 *A permutation C on symmetric group of a loop Q is called crypto-automorphism, if and only if $(R_mC, L_tC, C) \in \text{Atp}(Q)$, where $m, t \in Q$.*

Proof Suppose C is a crypto-automorphism, then by Definition 1.2 equation (1.4) holds in Q , ie $(x \cdot m)C \cdot (t \cdot y)C = (x \cdot y)C \Leftrightarrow xR_mC \cdot yL_tC = (xy)C \Leftrightarrow (R_mC, L_tC, C) \in \text{Atp}(Q)$. Thus the result follows. \square

Theorem 3.4 *Let (Q, \cdot) be a Buchsteiner loop. Then*

- (1) $T_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}$ is a crypto-automorphism with companions $v \setminus (v^\rho v)$ and v .
- (2) T_v is a crypto-automorphism with companions $v \setminus (v^\rho v)$ and v .

Proof (1) Using the autotopism $A = (T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}, T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v, T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v)$ in Corollary 3.3 such that for any $y, z \in Q$, we have

$$yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1} \cdot zT_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v = (yz)T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v.$$

If we set $z = 1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}R_v &= yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v \\ \Leftrightarrow yT_vL_{v^\lambda}L_v &= yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v \\ \Leftrightarrow yT_v(L_v^{-1}L_{v^\lambda}^{-1})^{-1} &= yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v \\ \Leftrightarrow yT_v(L_v^{-1}L_{v^\lambda}^{-1}L_{v^\lambda v})^{-1} &= yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v. \end{aligned}$$

From Theorem 2.1, we have $yT_vL_{(v, v^\lambda)} = yT_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v$. Thus we substitute to get $A = (T_vL_{v^\lambda}T_v^{-1}, T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}^{-1}T_v, T_vL_{(v, v^\lambda)})$.

Furthermore, $A^{-1} = (T_vL_{v^\lambda}^{-1}T_v^{-1}, T_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}T_v, L_{(v, v^\lambda)}^{-1}T_v^{-1})$, thus for any $y, z \in Q$, applying A^{-1} we obtain, $yT_vL_{v^\lambda}^{-1}T_v^{-1} \cdot zT_v^{-1}R_{v^\rho}T_v = (yz)L_{(v, v^\lambda)}^{-1}T_v^{-1}$. Now by appropriate calculation, we can re-write $A^{-1} = (L_{(v, v^\lambda)}^{-1}T_v^{-1}R_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}^{-1}, L_{(v^\lambda, v)}^{-1}T_v^{-1}L_v^{-1}, L_{(v^\lambda, v)}^{-1}T_v^{-1}) \Leftrightarrow A = (R_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}, L_vT_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}, T_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)})$, which proved (1).

(2) $L_{(v^\lambda, v)}$ has been observed to be an automorphism in Q ([5]). Thus taking any $a, b \in Q$, we can write from (1) that

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (R_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}, L_vT_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}, T_vL_{(v^\lambda, v)}) \\ &= (R_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_v, L_vT_v, T_v)(L_{(v^\lambda, v)}, L_{(v^\lambda, v)}, L_{(v^\lambda, v)}) \end{aligned}$$

and the result follows immediately. \square

Theorem 3.5 *Let Q be a Buchsteiner loop, then T_v^{-1} is a crypto-automorphism with companions v and $v^\lambda, \forall v \in Q$.*

Proof From Theorem 3.4(2), we observed that T_v is a crypto-automorphism with companions $(v \setminus (v^\rho v))$ and v , thus by definition it implies that, for any a and b in Q , we have $aR_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_v \cdot bL_vT_v = (ab)T_v$. Setting $b = a^\rho$, we obtain $aR_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_v \cdot a^\rho L_vT_v = 1 \Rightarrow R_{(v \setminus (v^\rho v))}T_v = J_\rho L_vT_v J_\lambda$, using the fact that Q is WWIP loop ([5]). This in terms of autotopism, implies $B = (J_\rho L_vT_v J_\lambda, L_vT_v, T_v) \in Atp(Q)$, finally by appropriate calculation we have $J_\lambda L_vT_v J_\rho = T_v R_v^{-1}$, and $L_vT_v = T_v L_{v^\lambda}^{-1}$, re-writing we have $B = (T_v R_v^{-1}, T_v L_{v^\lambda}^{-1}, T_v) \in Atp(Q), \forall v \in Q$. The result follows by taking the inverse of B . \square

Corollary 3.4 *Any Buchsteiner loop Q is an A -loop.*

Proof It is straight forward from Corollary 5.4 in [5] and the preceding theorem. \square

Remark 3.1 Since all the inner mappings, i.e. $L_{(u,v)}, R_{(u,v)}$ and T_v have been established to exhibit one form of automorphism or the other, then (Q, \cdot) is an A -loop.

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